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Бош муҳаррир:

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Таҳририят манзили: Тошкент шаҳар, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2/27-уй. Почта индекси 100152. Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz/com

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55, **E-mail:** tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

MUSAEV Djamaliddin Kamalovich
*Associate Professor of the Department
of Special Legal disciplines
of the Customs Institute*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11197566>

WAYS TO IMPROVE INTERACTION EFFICIENCY COUNTRIES - MEMBERS OF THE CIS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST ILLEGAL DRUG TRAFFICKING

ANNOTATION

The problem of the spread of drug addiction, abuse of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances is relevant in almost all countries of the world. Illicit drug trafficking has acquired a global scale in recent decades and has a very serious impact on the socio-psychological atmosphere in society, negatively affecting the economy, politics and law and order. In this regard, states are implementing a set of measures aimed at combating the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, including the creation of their own legal framework regulating the circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances in the territory of the CIS member countries.

Key words: crime, drug trafficking, smuggling, border security, cooperation, CIS, interaction between law enforcement agencies of the CIS countries.

МДҲГА АЪЗО ДАВЛАТЛАРНИНГ ГИЁҲВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРИНИ НОҚОНУНИЙ МУОМИЛАСИГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШДА ЎЗАРО ҲАМКОРЛИК САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Гиёҳвандлик воситалари ва психотроп моддаларни ноқонуний муомиласи дунёнинг деярли барча мамлакатларида долзарбдир. Гиёҳвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний айланиши сўнгги йилларда глобал миқёсга эга бўлиб, жамиятдаги ижтимоий-психологик муҳитга ўта жиддий таъсир кўрсатиб, иқтисодиёт, сиёсат ва ҳуқуқ-тартиботга салбий таъсир кўрсатмоқда. Шу муносабат билан давлатлар гиёҳвандлик воситалари ва психотроп моддаларнинг ноқонуний муомиласига қарши курашишда, жумладан, МДҲга аъзо давлатлар ҳудудида гиёҳвандлик воситалари ва психотроп моддаларнинг ноқонуний муомиласини тартибга солувчи ўз қонунчилик базасини яратишга қаратилган комплекс чора-тадбирларни амалга оширмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: жиноятчилик, МДҲ, гиёҳвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний муомиласи, контрабанда, чегара хавфсизлиги, ҳамкорлик, МДҲга аъзо давлатларнинг ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш органларининг ўзаро ҳамкорлиги.

ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ СТРАН - ЧЛЕНОВ СНГ В БОРЬБЕ С НЕЗАКОННЫМ ОБОРОТОМ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Проблема распространения наркомании, злоупотребления наркотическими средствами и психотропными веществами является актуальной практически во всех странах мира. Незаконный оборот наркотических средств приобрел в последние десятилетия глобальный масштаб и самым серьезным образом сказывается на социально психологической атмосфере в обществе, отрицательно влияет на экономику, политику и правопорядок. В связи с этим государствами осуществляются комплекс мер, направленных на борьбу с незаконным оборотом наркотических средств и психотропных веществ, включающих и создание своей правовой базы, регламентирующей оборот наркотических средств и психотропных веществ на территории стран-участниц СНГ.

Ключевые слова: преступление, незаконный оборот наркотических средств, контрабанда, безопасность границы, сотрудничество, СНГ, взаимодействие правоохранительных органов стран СНГ.

The intensive integration processes taking place in various parts of the world over the past decade indicate that in order to strengthen the fight against drug abuse and illicit trafficking, regional (subregional) cooperation between countries and the activities of regional bodies and organizations are becoming increasingly important.

While progress at the national level is paramount in the fight against drug crime, the ability of drug traffickers to redirect their operations from one state to another creates an urgent need for international joint work at the regional (subregional) level.

In recent years, clear encouraging results have been achieved thanks to the efforts of regional bodies and organizations, as well as the initiatives of individual coordinating (subregional) levels. bodies of the CIS at the regional Main directions of the fight against drug addiction:

- information and propaganda activities of a social and preventive nature;
- drug control and monitoring of illegal drug trafficking;
- voluntary and compulsory treatment of drug addicts;
- repressive measures to combat illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

Depending on the specific area, the designated joint work to combat drug abuse and drug trafficking has its own distinctive features; The work of regional organizations with single and special areas of responsibility is clearly highlighted.

The formation of integration actions in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) is a direct reflection of the internal political and socio-economic problems of the participating countries.

The existing differences in the texture of the economy and the stage of its reform, the socio-economic situation, and the geopolitical orientation of the Commonwealth states determine the choice and level of their socio-economic and military-political interaction.

Currently, across the CIS, integration "based on interests" is considered truly applicable and working for the newly independent countries (NIS). This is also supported by the fundamental documents of the CIS. They do not endow this international legal union of countries in general, or its individual executive bodies with supranational capabilities, and do not characterize the existing mechanisms for implementing decisions made. The form of countries' roles in the Commonwealth does not actually impose on them virtually any responsibilities.

Thus, in accordance with the Rules of Procedure of the Council of Heads of State and the Council of Heads of Government of the CIS, any state included in it can declare its disinterest in a particular issue, which is not considered an obstacle to decision-making."

This allows each state to choose forms of participation in the Commonwealth and areas of cooperation. In connection with the above, it is of scientific and practical interest to study the experience of bilateral and regional cooperation of states in the fight against drug trafficking and, first of all, its legal basis in order to further improve the forms of such activity.

The main attention should be paid to the analysis of the legal basis for cooperation between states in the fight against drug trafficking within the framework of the Commonwealth of Independent States. As noted above, the problem of illegal drug trafficking is a transnational problem and requires the most active solution.

M. Yu. Kiyko notes that “the economic damage to our country only from Afghan opiates due to the calculation of drug addicts from the economic active population, the costs of their treatment, the costs of the penitentiary system, legal costs, etc. is estimated at an amount equal to the losses 3% of GDP, which is approximately two times 56 more than the United States spends on military operations and its presence in Afghanistan” [1].

At the last 13th UN Congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice (April 12-19, 2015, Doha), the “Doha Declaration” [2] was adopted, which, among other things, enshrines the need to intensify the efforts of all states to solve the global drug problem (para. 1 section 8), as well as the need to develop preventive work in the activities of criminal justice authorities (clause “a” of section 9).

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime's World Report 2022[3] states: “Globally, 2021 estimates, no illicit drugs – predominantly cannabis, opioids, cocaine or amphetamine-type stimulants – although 162 to 324 million people used drugs once during the previous year, which corresponds to 3.5-7.0% of the world population aged 15-64 years (at the same time, the number of people who regularly use drugs ranges from 16 to 39 million . people)”.

And if we approach the problem of drug addiction and narcotism as a well-established and effectively functioning economic sector, then we must confront this negative phenomenon with knowledge of the legislative framework and using the full power of society and the state. Otherwise, not only the economy of the state will suffer significantly and may be undermined, but the very existence of the state will be in immediate danger.

In addition, the interest of criminal structures in the credit, financial and foreign economic spheres, in the securities market is expanding, and the number of illegal transactions for the export of raw materials, energy and other resources abroad is increasing. The annual number of detected economic crimes increases by 17–20%. According to expert estimates, organized criminal groups control up to 50% of private and up to 60% of state-owned enterprises.

The outflow of domestic capital abroad continues; it amounts to between 1 and 1.5 billion US dollars every month [4].

In recent years, another very serious trend has been observed: the drug business is already finding it difficult to develop only in the economic sphere; it is also breaking into the sphere of public administration and politics.

He needs such orders and laws, such authorities that would provide optimal conditions for his prosperity. The drug business is part of organized crime and, having large, steadily growing financial resources, counteracts and confronts government authorities and management in their activities to implement the state will, and reduces confidence in it on the part of citizens.

The confrontation and opposition of the drug business to the legitimate activities of state authorities and management is not only criminal, but also political in nature, since, by undermining the basic principles of state power and management, it can lead to a distortion and reorientation of the state's political course. Currently, there are no targeted comprehensive programs to combat drug trafficking and drug abuse between the CIS member countries.

Not all CIS countries have created funds to support measures aimed at crime prevention, and in places where such funds have been created, they have not yet fully demonstrated themselves, especially in terms of implementing items that require monetary expenditures.

Effective counteraction to drug trafficking crimes is significantly influenced by the following:

- the problem of insufficient professional training of persons empowered in the field of combating the types of crimes under consideration;
- procedural errors when documenting crimes related to drug trafficking;
- insufficiently competent and complete support of criminal cases, which is why many criminal cases are subsequently terminated or returned for further investigation.

This problem is typical for many countries. In the fight against drug trafficking, repressive measures against drug traffickers are also important. In some countries of Southeast Asia (China, Iraq, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, Nigeria), corporal punishment and even the death penalty have been introduced for drug distribution.

Thus, in Singapore, if an accused possesses more than 15 g of heroin or 30 g of morphine or 500 g of marijuana, he is punishable by death. In the United States, in some states, distribution of drugs is punishable by death or imprisonment for a term of 15 to 30 years.

Based on the above, we believe that for a more successful fight against illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, the following priorities for the near future should be considered:

1. Strengthening the borders of the CIS countries in order to identify and block drug distribution channels.
2. Adoption of additional measures, not of a declarative nature, to strengthen interaction between the relevant services of the drug transit regions of the CIS countries.
3. Intensification of the work of the CIS member states to expose financial structures involved in drug legalization.
4. The adoption by all CIS states of procedural measures aimed at undermining the economic basis of drug crime, in terms of securing, confiscating and arresting funds and other property acquired by criminal means, with a view to their further confiscation to the state, not only from persons convicted of illegal drug trafficking, but also their close relatives.
5. Strengthening efforts to bring drug traffickers to justice (actively using the operational investigative activity method - test purchase), simplifying the procedural procedure for its registration.
6. There is a need for systematic work by all law enforcement agencies of the Russian Federation and CIS countries to expose and eliminate organized crime groups and gangs of drug traffickers, to identify the entire chain of drug trafficking - from manufacturers to persons involved in the laundering of funds obtained by criminal means.

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Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

Эл. почта: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz